

**L'INTERFÉRENCE DE L'ARABE MAROCAIN SUR LE FRANÇAIS
AU COLLÈGE : CAS DE L'ORAL AU MAROC /**

**THE INTERFERENCE OF MOROCCAN ARABIC ON FRENCH
IN MIDDLE SCHOOL: A CASE STUDY OF SPOKEN LANGUAGE IN MOROCCO**

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In multilingual education systems, teaching French as a foreign language (FLE) presents complex challenges, particularly in the area of oral production. In Morocco, where several languages coexist (dialectal Arabic, Amazigh, Classical Arabic, and French), students often encounter specific difficulties when expressing themselves orally in French. These difficulties are not solely due to limited vocabulary or grammatical knowledge; rather, they are deeply rooted in the linguistic and cognitive phenomenon of interference.

Linguistic interference occurs when learners unconsciously transfer elements from their mother tongue, such as vocabulary, phonetics, or syntax, into the foreign language they are learning. In the case of Moroccan middle school students, this transfer often manifests through pronunciation errors, gender confusion, lexical calques, and grammatical constructions influenced by dialectal Arabic or Tamazight.

Oral proficiency is a central objective in FLE instruction, particularly at the middle school level, where students must be prepared to interact, debate, express themselves clearly, and understand others in a language that is not their own. In this context, it becomes essential to systematically study the impact of linguistic interference on students' oral production, both to understand its mechanisms and causes, and to develop effective teaching strategies to mitigate its effects.

Our communication aligns with this objective. It aims to explore the most frequent types of linguistic interference among 3rd-year middle school students, to analyze the contributing factors, and to examine their influence on oral performance.